

Hybrid AI and Multi-Criteria Decision-Making for Predicting and Managing Supply Chain Disruptions: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract—Supply chains are increasingly exposed to disruptions caused by pandemics, geopolitical shocks, natural hazards, labour shortages, and infrastructure failures. This paper investigates how artificial intelligence (AI), and multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) are being combined to predict, assess, and manage such disruptions. The study adopts a systematic literature review approach, guided by PRISMA principles, to examine research published between 2020 and 2025 on hybrid AI-MCDM approaches for supply chain disruption management. The review analyses the AI techniques used, the MCDM methods applied, their main application areas, the types of data employed, and the evaluation measures reported. The findings indicate a growing shift towards hybrid decision-support frameworks in which machine learning and deep learning provide predictive capability, while MCDM methods improve prioritisation, transparency, and managerial interpretability. The most common application areas include supplier selection, risk assessment, resilience evaluation, and logistics planning. At the same time, the literature reveals persistent limitations, including reliance on synthetic or simulation-based datasets, limited real-world validation, and challenges in balancing predictive performance with explainability. The paper contributes a structured overview of current research trends and highlights the need for more robust, real-time, and interpretable hybrid frameworks to support resilient and sustainable supply chain decision-making under uncertainty.

Index Terms—Supply chain disruption, Supply chain resilience, Artificial intelligence, Machine learning, Multi-criteria decision-making, Systematic literature review

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent years have been characterised by a range of disruptive events, such as COVID-19-related shortages [1], Toyota’s semiconductor constraints [2], Marks & Spencer’s post-Brexit supply issues [3], and the Ever Given blockage of the Suez Canal [4] have demonstrated how vulnerable contemporary supply chains are to sudden and interconnected shocks. These events have intensified pressures that were already being shaped by geopolitical instability, climate-related risks, labour shortages, cyber threats, and rising sustainability expectations. As a result, supply chain disruption management has become a major area of interest for both researchers and practitioners,

particularly where decision-makers must act rapidly under uncertainty and with incomplete information.

In response to this challenge, recent studies have increasingly explored hybrid modelling approaches that combine artificial intelligence (AI) with multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) techniques. In such approaches, AI methods provide prediction, classification, or optimisation capability, while MCDM methods support structured prioritisation, trade-off analysis, and managerial interpretability. This combination is especially appealing in disruption-sensitive settings, where predictive performance alone may be insufficient if the resulting recommendations are difficult to justify or operationalise [5]. Related work has shown how sustainability-oriented digital supply chain frameworks can be prioritised using hybrid Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set (IFS), Analytic Network Process (ANP) and Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) methods [6], while other studies have introduced hybrid optimisation and MCDM approaches to strengthen sustainable and resilient supply chain design [7]. Additional work has proposed integrated synthetic evaluation approaches to support resilience and sustainability objectives [8]. This research lends support to the claim that hybrid AI-MCDM models can offer a more adaptive, transparent, and robust basis for decision-making under uncertainty.

Despite this growing interest, the literature remains fragmented across application domains, modelling choices, data sources, and evaluation practices. Some studies focus on supplier selection, while others address delay forecasting, risk assessment, resilience evaluation, sustainability trade-offs, or logistics planning. Similarly, studies differ in the types of AI techniques and MCDM methods used, the sectors they examine, and the extent to which they report interpretable and operationally useful outcomes. A focused synthesis is therefore needed to clarify how hybrid AI-MCDM approaches are currently being used for supply chain disruption management, where they have shown promise, and where important limitations remain.

This study addresses the following research questions:

RQ1. Which AI and MCDM techniques are most commonly

combined in supply chain disruption management research?

RQ2. In which application areas are hybrid AI-MCDM approaches being used, and how are they evaluated?

RQ3. What limitations and research gaps characterise the current literature on hybrid AI-MCDM approaches for supply chain disruption management?

The paper contributes a systematic synthesis of recent literature on hybrid AI-MCDM methodologies, identifies recurring limitations in current practice, and highlights future research directions for more resilient, transparent, and sustainable supply chain decision-making.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Supply Chain Disruption and Resilience

A supply chain disruption is an unforeseen event that interrupts the flow of materials, products, or information across the supply network [9]. Since supply chains operate as interconnected networks, localised disturbances can propagate across tiers and regions and create wider ripple effects [10]. Supply chains can also be viewed as complex adaptive systems, since they exhibit interdependence, nonlinear interactions, and adaptive behaviour across multiple actors and tiers [11]. In this context, resilience is commonly understood through capabilities such as robustness, agility, and adaptability [12]. More recently, the discussion has expanded towards long-term viability [13]–[15], which emphasises the ability of a supply chain to sustain operations during prolonged and unpredictable disruption.

Sustainability is also increasingly recognised as an important component of resilience. Environmentally efficient operations, social responsibility, and economic stability can all strengthen the capacity of supply chains to absorb shocks and recover more effectively [16]. Similarly, circular economy practices and data-driven visibility have been associated with reduced disruption exposure, improved resource flexibility, and stronger recovery mechanisms [17]–[19]. These developments suggest that disruption management can no longer be treated solely as a short-term risk mitigation problem, but must increasingly be understood in relation to broader resilience and sustainability objectives.

B. AI and MCDM in Disruption Management

Multi-criteria decision-making provides a structured way to evaluate alternatives when multiple and often conflicting criteria must be balanced. A range of MCDM methods are relevant in disruption settings because they can formalise trade-offs among cost, resilience, sustainability, service level, and risk [20]. These methods are often used to support supplier ranking, disruption response prioritisation, resilience assessment, and strategic planning under uncertainty.

In parallel, AI and machine learning techniques such as artificial neural networks (ANN), support vector machines (SVM), random forests (RF), reinforcement learning, deep learning and graph-based AI [21] have been applied to forecasting, anomaly detection, supplier assessment, delay prediction, and recovery planning. Although these techniques can improve

predictive capability, the opacity of many high-performing models has increased interest in hybrid AI-MCDM frameworks, where predictive methods are combined with more transparent decision structures [5], [22]. Hybridisation is therefore attractive not only because it combines complementary analytical strengths, but also because it can help bridge the gap between technical performance and managerial trust.

C. Research Gap

Recent literature has highlighted the growing importance of hybrid and data-driven approaches to supply chain resilience and disruption management [5], [23], [24]. Existing studies point to the value of combining predictive analytics with structured decision support, particularly in contexts that require explainability, sustainability considerations, and rapid response to disruption. However, existing reviews tend either to discuss AI in supply chains more broadly or to examine MCDM and resilience from a more conceptual perspective [25], [26]. A focused review of hybrid AI-MCDM approaches in disruption management is therefore useful in order to bring together dispersed evidence on techniques, application areas, evaluation practices, and recurring limitations.

III. METHODS

This systematic literature review was conducted in accordance with PRISMA principles [27] and focused on studies published between 2020 and 2025 that combine AI and MCDM in the context of supply chain disruption management.

A. Eligibility Criteria

Studies were included if they were peer-reviewed journal articles published in English, explicitly combined at least one AI technique with at least one MCDM method, and addressed supply chain disruption management, resilience, or closely related decision problems. Studies were excluded if they lacked either an AI component or an MCDM component, did not have a clear supply chain disruption focus, were not peer reviewed, or were duplicate records. Conference abstracts and non-scholarly materials were also excluded in order to maintain consistency in the review corpus.

B. Information Sources and Search Strategy

The review combined a curated dataset of 67 papers with additional database searches. Searches were conducted between January 2025 and March 2025 across ScienceDirect, SpringerLink, Emerald Insight, MDPI, and IEEE Xplore. The search strategy combined terms related to AI, machine learning, deep learning, MCDM, supply chain resilience, and disruption management. A representative search logic followed the form: ("AI" OR "Artificial Intelligence" OR "Machine Learning" OR "Deep Learning") AND ("MCDM" OR "Multi-Criteria Decision Making") AND ("Supply Chain Resilience" OR "Disruption Management"). Search strings were refined iteratively to improve relevance and coverage.

Fig. 1. Study selection process stages.

C. Selection Process

Database searching yielded 150 records. After the removal of 30 duplicates, 120 records remained for title and abstract screening. Following this stage, 35 studies were retained for full-text assessment. An additional 34 studies were identified through reference inspection and backwards snowballing, resulting in a final sample of 69 studies. Screening decisions were discussed between the authors to improve consistency in study selection.

D. Data Extraction and Synthesis

A structured data extraction form was used to record bibliographic details, AI techniques, MCDM methods, application area, industry context, dataset type, validation approach, and evaluation metrics for each study. This allowed comparisons to be made across methodological choices and application settings. The findings were synthesised descriptively in order to identify dominant patterns in the literature, including commonly used AI and MCDM combinations, the most prominent areas of application, and the main methodological limitations reported across studies.

E. Quality Considerations

Although no formal scoring was applied, quality-related issues were examined during the review. Particular attention was given to the nature of the datasets used, the degree of methodological transparency, the presence or absence of real-world validation, and the clarity with which evaluation procedures were reported. These considerations informed the interpretation of the findings and the discussion of limitations in the literature.

IV. RESULTS

This section summarises the reviewed literature in terms of the AI techniques used, the MCDM methods adopted, the main application areas, the types of datasets employed, and the evaluation practices reported. Overall, the reviewed studies indicate growing interest in hybrid AI-MCDM approaches for disruption prediction, supplier selection, resilience evaluation, and logistics planning.

Fig. 2. Distribution of AI techniques used in the reviewed studies (2020–2025).

TABLE I
DISTRIBUTION OF AI TECHNIQUES IN REVIEWED STUDIES (2020–2025).

AI Technique	Frequency
Random Forest (RF)	19
Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)	14
Support Vector Machines (SVM)	12
Optimisation	10
Machine Learning (generic)	7
Decision Tree	4
Fuzzy Logic	3

A. Study Selection

The study selection process is summarised in Fig. 1. Following database searching, duplicate removal, title and abstract screening, and full-text assessment, a final set of 69 studies was retained for descriptive synthesis. The final sample combines a curated core of publications with a smaller number of additional studies identified through database searching, allowing the review to cover both established and more recent contributions.

B. Descriptive Analysis

The descriptive analysis summarises the reviewed studies in terms of the AI methods used, MCDM methods employed, application areas, dataset types, and reported evaluation measures. This analysis shows that the field is heterogeneous, both in the technical combinations used and in the decision problems being addressed.

1) *AI Techniques Distribution*: The reviewed studies reveal frequent use of machine learning and deep learning methods such as ANN, SVM, RF, and reinforcement learning. These techniques are primarily used for predictive analytics, disruption identification, supplier assessment, classification of disruption scenarios, and decision support. Figure 2 and Table I summarise the most common AI techniques reported in the literature.

The prominence of RF, ANN, and SVM suggests that the literature continues to favour techniques that are both established and flexible across different disruption-related tasks. RF

TABLE II
MOST FREQUENTLY REPORTED MCDM METHODS IN REVIEWED STUDIES.

MCDM Method	Frequency
AHP	6
TOPSIS	4
VIKOR	2
DEMATEL	1

TABLE III
APPLICATION AREAS IDENTIFIED IN REVIEWED STUDIES.

Application Area	Frequency
Resilience Evaluation	16
Risk Assessment	12
Supplier Selection	11
Logistics Optimisation	4
Demand Forecasting	1
Sustainability Assessment	1

is especially well suited to tabular and heterogeneous operational data, while SVM and ANN have been used in settings where classification accuracy is prioritised. The inclusion of optimisation-oriented methods also indicates that the field does not view AI only as a predictive tool, but increasingly as part of a broader decision-analytic pipeline that may include search, ranking, and resource allocation components.

2) *MCDM Methods Distribution*: Across the reviewed literature, AHP and TOPSIS appear among the most commonly used MCDM methods, often because of their relative simplicity and interpretability. Other frequently reported methods include VIKOR, DEMATEL, ANP, and Best-Worst Method (BWM). Table II summarises the most frequently reported MCDM methods among the studies that explicitly identified method-specific usage counts.

In many hybrid frameworks, MCDM methods are used to weight disruption criteria, rank suppliers or response strategies, or support trade-off analysis among resilience, sustainability, cost, and service considerations [28]–[31]. This indicates that MCDM plays a central role not only as an add-on, but as a mechanism for translating predictive outputs into more structured managerial decisions. The use of methods such as DEMATEL and ANP also shows that disruption drivers can be interdependent rather than independent, which is particularly important in networked and cascading risk environments [32], [33].

3) *Application Areas*: The most frequently discussed application areas include resilience evaluation, risk assessment, supplier selection, and logistics optimisation. This concentration suggests that hybrid AI-MCDM research has mostly focused on strengthening decision-making in areas where disruption exposure and managerial trade-offs are especially pronounced.

The dominance of resilience evaluation and risk assessment points to the fact that much of the literature is still concentrated on identifying vulnerabilities, assessing disruption exposure, and prioritising mitigation actions, rather than on fully operational real-time decision execution. Supplier selection is another major area because supplier-related decisions naturally involve multiple criteria and are highly sensitive to disruption,

TABLE IV
TYPES OF DATASETS USED IN REVIEWED STUDIES.

Dataset Type	Frequency
Real-world data	38
Simulation data	20
Synthetic data	11

TABLE V
MOST FREQUENTLY REPORTED PERFORMANCE METRICS.

Metric	Frequency
Accuracy	7
RMSE	5
Precision	3
Recall	3
F1-Score	2
MAPE	2
Error Rate / MAE	2
Others (e.g., R^2 , AUC, efficiency)	1

sustainability, and quality considerations. Logistics optimisation and forecasting appear less frequently in the reviewed corpus, but these areas may become more prominent as real-time data availability and digital infrastructure continue to improve.

Beyond these aggregate categories, the reviewed studies span a range of sectors including transportation, electronics, automotive, pharmaceuticals, food, retail, and humanitarian logistics. This cross-sector spread indicates that hybrid AI-MCDM approaches are not restricted to a single industrial context, although many contributions remain tailored to specific operational problems and datasets.

4) *Dataset Types*: Most studies relied on real-world or case-based datasets, while a smaller number used simulation-based or synthetic data. This pattern indicates a gradual shift towards more empirical evaluation, although non-operational data sources remain common.

The relatively strong presence of real-world data is encouraging because it suggests that at least part of the literature is engaging with practical operational complexity rather than relying solely on crafted scenarios. However, the continued use of simulation and synthetic data also highlights the persistent difficulty of. On the one hand, simulated data can be useful for stress testing rare disruption scenarios and examining hypothetical policies. On the other hand, heavy reliance on such data can limit the external validity of results, especially where operational constraints, missing data, or human decision behaviour are difficult to model realistically.

5) *Performance Metrics*: Accuracy, root mean square error (RMSE), precision, recall, F1-score, and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) were among the most frequently reported performance metrics. These measures reflect the mixed use of classification, regression, and ranking tasks across the reviewed studies. They also suggest that studies have tended to focus more strongly on predictive performance than on broader issues such as interpretability, usability, or deployment readiness.

This metric profile shows that the literature continues to pri-

Distribution of Performance Metrics in Reviewed Studies (2020–2025)

Fig. 3. Distribution of performance metrics used across reviewed studies (2020–2025).

oritise technical evaluation over decision-process evaluation. Very few studies, at least in a systematic and comparable way, appear to assess whether hybrid approaches improve managerial understanding, trust, adoption, or decision quality in live settings. This is notable because the main justification for combining AI with MCDM is often precisely the expectation that such systems will support better and more explainable decisions.

C. Synthesis of Findings

The reviewed literature shows a clear increase in the use of hybrid AI-MCDM frameworks for supply chain disruption management. Most studies combine predictive AI techniques with structured decision-support methods, enabling organisations to move from disruption detection or forecasting to prioritisation and action selection. The most common application areas are supplier selection, risk assessment, resilience evaluation, and logistics-related planning.

Two broad integration patterns are visible in the literature. In sequential frameworks, AI techniques are first used to predict risks, classify disruption scenarios, or estimate operational outcomes, after which MCDM methods are applied to rank alternatives or support decision selection [34]. In more tightly integrated frameworks, AI and MCDM components are combined within a single decision pipeline to balance predictive capability with interpretability. The former pattern appears especially relevant where the predictive and decision stages are clearly separable, while the latter is more suitable where disruption response requires closer coupling between analytics and prioritisation.

The review also indicates that hybridisation is being used for different purposes across the literature. In some studies, MCDM acts mainly as a post-processing layer that helps

decision-makers interpret AI outputs and compare alternatives transparently. In others, MCDM is embedded earlier in the process, for example by informing feature weighting, criteria structuring, or model selection. This variation supports the view of hybrid AI-MCDM as not simply a single architecture, but rather as a family of approaches that differ in how tightly prediction and decision support are linked.

Recent studies also show increasing interest in integrating sustainability objectives into disruption-sensitive decision models, particularly where resilience, cost, and environmental criteria must be considered jointly [7], [8]. This suggests that hybrid AI-MCDM research is expanding beyond immediate operational risk and towards more strategic assessments of viable and sustainable supply chain design. Related work on digital platforms, traceability, and digital twins further points to the growing role of data infrastructure in enabling more responsive hybrid decision-support systems [35]–[37].

A recurring theme across the literature is the trade-off between predictive performance and explainability [38], [39]. More complex machine learning and deep learning models [40] often offer stronger predictive capability, but their opacity can reduce managerial trust. MCDM methods help address this challenge by introducing transparent criteria structures and explicit prioritisation logic. However, the evidence base remains constrained by limited real-world validation, uneven reporting of methodological details, and continued reliance on simulation or synthetic data in a substantial part of the literature. Overall, the findings suggest that the main value of hybrid AI-MCDM lies primarily in the possibility of making disruption-sensitive decisions more structured, transparent, and justifiable.

D. Risk of Bias and Quality Assessment

Several recurring quality issues were identified across the reviewed studies. First, many papers relied on simulation-based or synthetic datasets, which limits the external validity of their findings. Second, real-world validation remained relatively limited, with many frameworks evaluated using historical or hypothetical data rather than live operational settings. Third, methodological reporting was often incomplete, particularly with respect to data preprocessing, parameter settings, evaluation design, and the exact role played by the MCDM component within the hybrid pipeline. These issues reduce reproducibility and make cross-study comparison more difficult.

A further consideration is that studies reporting positive or promising results may be more likely to appear in the published literature than studies with weaker or null findings. Although this review did not attempt formal publication bias assessment, the possibility of selective reporting should be acknowledged when interpreting the apparent effectiveness of hybrid AI-MCDM approaches. There is also a risk that some studies conflate predictive performance with decision usefulness, without showing that the hybrid system actually improves decisions in practice.

Taken together, these issues suggest that stronger empirical validation, clearer reporting practices, and greater use of open or industrial datasets would improve the reliability and practical relevance of future work. More explicit reporting of how criteria are elicited, weighted, and validated would also strengthen the credibility of hybrid AI-MCDM studies, especially in settings where stakeholder judgement plays an important role [41].

V. DISCUSSION

The review confirms that hybrid AI-MCDM approaches offer a promising basis for supply chain disruption management because they combine predictive capability with structured and more interpretable decision support. This is particularly valuable in disruption contexts, where managers must act under uncertainty while balancing operational, economic, and increasingly sustainability-related criteria. The literature also indicates that hybrid approaches are being used not only for forecasting and classification, but also for ranking alternatives, evaluating resilience drivers, and supporting supplier and logistics decisions.

From a practical perspective, the findings suggest that hybrid approaches are most useful where organisations require not only accurate predictions, but also clear justification for recommended actions. In disruption-sensitive environments, the value of a model depends not simply on whether it predicts accurately, but also on whether its outputs can be explained, compared, and acted upon in a way that aligns with organisational priorities. This makes the combination of AI and MCDM particularly relevant for managerial settings where trust, accountability, and trade-off visibility matter. In other words, the hybrid paradigm is attractive not because it replaces managerial judgement, but because it can structure and support that judgement more effectively.

The review also points to an important conceptual shift within the literature. Early work in AI for supply chains often focused primarily on prediction and optimisation, while more recent hybrid work increasingly emphasises interpretability, explainability, prioritisation, and sustainability-aware decision support. This shift is significant because disruption management is rarely a purely technical problem. It typically involves balancing competing objectives, differing stakeholder perspectives, and operational constraints that are not always easily captured through a single predictive metric. Hybrid AI-MCDM approaches are therefore well positioned to address the socio-technical character of disruption management.

At the same time, the field remains methodologically uneven. Although many studies report encouraging results, the literature is still shaped by limited industrial validation, incomplete reporting standards, and a tendency to emphasise technical performance over practical deployment. Many studies remain proof-of-concept in nature, demonstrating that hybridisation is feasible without fully showing that it is robust, scalable, or readily deployable in live organisational settings. This identifies a need for research that moves beyond proof-of-concept hybrid models towards more transparent and em-

pirically validated decision-support systems that can operate in real or near-real-time environments.

Several specific priorities emerge for future research. First, there is a need to explore a wider range of hybrid architectures, not only in terms of which AI or MCDM approaches are included, but also the nature of the hybrid (i.e. sequential, parallel or combinations). Second, more studies should examine hybrid architectures in operational environments and across multiple sectors, rather than within single-case or highly crafted settings. Third, stronger attention should be given to human-AI interaction, including how decision-makers understand, trust, and challenge hybrid recommendations. Fourth, future work should compare different forms of hybridisation more explicitly, for example sequential versus more integrated architectures, in order to clarify which designs are best suited to different disruption contexts. Finally, there is scope for greater integration of sustainability, viability, and resilience into unified decision frameworks rather than treating these dimensions separately [42].

The findings also suggest that digital infrastructure is becoming increasingly important [43], [44]. As data pipelines, traceability platforms, and digital twin environments mature, hybrid AI-MCDM approaches may become more capable of supporting dynamic and context-aware disruption management. However, this will also raise new questions about data quality, governance, transparency, and the alignment between automated analytics and human oversight. Consequently, future research should not focus only on better models, but also on how such models fit within broader organisational processes, governance structures, and digital ecosystems.

Overall, the literature indicates that hybrid AI-MCDM is a promising but still developing area. Its future contribution will depend less on isolated improvements in predictive performance and more on whether researchers can design systems that are interpretable, empirically grounded, and genuinely useful for decision-makers facing complex and evolving disruptions.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper reviewed recent literature on hybrid AI-MCDM approaches for supply chain disruption management published between 2020 and 2025. The review shows growing interest in frameworks that combine predictive analytics with structured decision-support methods, particularly in supplier selection, risk assessment, resilience evaluation, and logistics planning. However, the literature is still limited by inconsistent validation practices, incomplete methodological reporting, and relatively little real-world deployment. Future work should prioritise stronger empirical validation, clearer reporting, and the development of more interpretable and operationally deployable hybrid frameworks.

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